

Treatment wetlands as a part of municipal wastewater treatment

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Abstract

This study has analysed 12 years of operational data from seven Swedish wastewater treatment wetlands combined with operator interviews and results of previous studies. Previous studies indicate that wetlands apart from nitrogen and phosphorus even effectively remove pathogens and micropollutants. The aim of this study was to summarize and make available knowledge on reduction efficiency for nitrogen, phosphorous, pathogens and drug residues of wastewater treatment wetlands used as a complimentary step for municipal wastewater treatment plants.

The examined wetlands remove between 500 and 2 000 kg of nitrogen per year and hectare, depending on load and design. By creating wetlands, requirements for nitrogen purification can thus be met with lower energy consumption and/or addition of carbon source in the treatment plant. Phosphorous removal in the examined wetlands is proportional to phosphorus load. Given that the treatment plant is equipped with a flocculation step, phosphorus concentrations in the effluent of treatment wetlands vary between 0,05 and 0,1 mg/l. Construction of wetlands before discharging to recipient water bodies even reduces the risk for pathogen contamination, something that is of particular importance for smaller water bodies or such ones that feature nearby bathing areas.

Treatment wetlands aimed at nitrification of ammonium have the highest removal of pharmaceutical residues. Removal is highest during summer due to higher biological activity. There are uncertainties in the reduction efficiency of persistent substances that are difficult to degrade as well as what happens to the degradation products.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Nitrogen; pharmaceuticals; phosphorous; treatment wetlands; wastewater;

INTRODUCTION

In the early 1990s several Swedish wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) began to use treatment wetlands as a part of their treatment process. The wetlands constitute a complementary treatment step, as they together with the traditional treatment processes in the plant, allow far-reaching purification, provided they are designed and dimensioned correctly. Several studies on the function of these wetlands have shown that, in addition to the removal of nitrogen and phosphorus, they even effectively remove pathogens and micropollutants.

The study was conducted by WRS AB in cooperation with Eskilstuna Strängnäs Energi och Miljö AB (WWTP operator in Eskilstuna municipality), Nynäshamn municipality, Oxelö Energi (WWTP operators in Oxelösunds municipality), Region Gotland (WWTP operator on the island of Gotland) and Växjö municipality.

The treatment processes in wetlands are essentially the same as those used in traditional sewage treatment plants, but instead being driven by electricity (aeration for example) or the addition of carbon sources, they are instead driven by sunlight and gravity. The key processes in wetlands are sedimentation including sorption, and biological degradation/transformation.

METHODS

This study consists of three parts; a study of operating data from 2010 until 2022 from seven Swedish treatment wetlands; interviews with WWTP operators and a literature review.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Nitrogen retention

A treatment wetland can be expected to reduce 500–2000 kg of nitrogen/ha and year depending on wetland design and nitrogen load. Parameters affecting reduction efficiency are:

- the load and the chemical form in which nitrogen occurs.
- wetland design (intermittently inundated sheet flow areas are required for nitrification while permanently inundated wetlands with emergent vegetation appear to be better for denitrification.
- wetland size, i.e. the area that can produce biomass, controls the availability of carbon for denitrification.

There is a clear seasonal variation regarding the removal of nitrogen where the removal rates are highest during summer and lower at lower temperatures. Typical residual nitrogen levels in effluent from the wetlands are 3–10 mg/l during the summer months. Anammox processes have been shown to contribute to nitrogen separation in treatment wetlands in temperate climates and could contribute to nitrogen transformation in Swedish conditions.

Phosphorus retention

Phosphorous concentrations in the effluent of studied wetlands vary from 0.05 mg/l to 1.2 mg/l. Highest reduction is observed in wetlands with a long hydraulic residence time, dense stands of emergent vegetation and a high proportion of particulate phosphorus in WWTP effluent.

With the exception of periods with operational problems in WWTPs, outgoing phosphorus levels in all studied wetlands have been stable over the years. No significant loss of phosphorous retention capacity can be observed over time. A certain seasonal variation can be observed with slightly higher outgoing concentrations in summer and lower ones during winter. Evaporation during summer months is one likely factor for increased concentrations. Another explanation maybe mobilization of phosphorous into plankton biomass present in outflowing water in summer. A third mechanism that could explain summer concentrations is the release of chemically bound phosphorus from sediments in the absence of oxygen and nitrate as a result of biological decomposition processes.

There is a clear correlation between phosphorus reduction and total phosphorus load. Low load and long hydraulic residence time favor increased phosphorus reduction.

Reduction of pathogens

Concentrations of indicator bacterial pathogens decreases rapidly during the water's residence time in the studied wetlands. From levels around 10^3 – 10^4 cfu/100 ml at the inlets to 10^1 – 10^2 cfu/100 ml at the outlets. As no major differences are observed between seasons, pathogen reduction is likely mainly caused by filtration and sedimentation. The conclusion is also strengthened by the observed correlation between pathogen separation and the reduction of suspended material. Wetlands designed with long residence times feature higher pathogen separation than wetlands with shorter residence times.

Reduction of pharmaceutical residues

Data for the separation of micropollutants including pharmaceutical residues in Swedish wastewater wetlands has been obtained from five wastewater treatment wetlands in south and central Sweden. Of ten reported pharmaceutical substances, removal efficiencies were highest for diclofenac, ibuprofen and trimethoprim. The results are in line with expectations for ibuprofen, a substance that

degrades easily but more unexpected for diclofenac, which normally is more persistent.

Figure 1. Removal efficiencies of detected pharmaceuticals from the EU's watch list (EUB), the EU Commission's proposal for priority substances in the new sewage directive (EUP) and the Norwegian Sea and Water Authority's list of particularly polluting substances, in five Swedish wastewater treatment wetlands (each wetland represented with a unique color). The number indicates the change in concentration reduction for sulfamethoxazole. The number of analyses of the observed removal efficiencies are based on vary between wetlands and substances.

Comparison between summer and winter samplings shows consistently higher removal during the summer. Most likely this is due to higher biological activity at higher temperatures but even higher solar radiation and particularly higher levels of UV-light during summer may play an important role in the degradation of certain substances. The fact that removal efficiencies vary between wetlands can be the result of differences in wetland design. Wetlands that feature intermittently inundated sheet flow areas for nitrification as well as deeper parts for denitrification, such as Brannäs, Alhagen and Trosa show higher removal rates in both summer and winter than wetlands that only feature permanently inundated areas such Ekeby and Magle.

Even if our results provide a good indication of the potential for constructed wetlands to effectively remove pharmaceutical residues from wastewater in Nordic conditions, there is still a considerable need for more comprehensive study to better understand how to use wetland in the best possible way. The observed higher removal efficiencies in wetlands with intermittently inundated sheet flow areas is a good indication that high redox potential leads to higher removal rates.

For several substances degradation could not be observed since their concentrations in either influent or effluent were below the analytical method's detection limit. However, for many substances, such as hormones, even levels below detection limits can pose a threat to aquatic

environments. Technological progress will likely result in lower detection levels, lower costs and new analysis techniques for emerging substances of concern. This in turn can lead to more comprehensive studies into the fate of pharmaceutical residues in wetlands. Key questions to answer include which processes are responsible for degradation, which degradation products arise and whether or not degradation products have any adverse effects on the environment or human health themselves.

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